

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the privacy and security modules of the Ageing@Work platform, in order to protect sensitive data and elicit trust to the end-users. Given the pervasiveness of the involved technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality and multimodal data collection, potential threats and risks of their use along with possible conflicts in respect to the relationship between employer and employee, had to be identified and addressed successfully.

A clear overview of security and privacy requirements and ethical aspects has already been provided in D2.8 (Ageing@Work System Architecture). This information is further detailed in the present document with a focus on the development of a conceptual framework to protect privacy and security by addressing trust and confidentiality issues within smart workplaces. In the current document an overview of the necessary security measurements and corrective actions that have been implemented with respect to the general digital platform of the Ageing@Work system as well as to each digital tool, in order to ensure the privacy and security workers' data.

Furthermore, the core technical components and specifications of the system used for workers' data protection are illustrated herein. The security and privacy modules as specified and implemented to ensure security and privacy of data processing operations are described along with security and privacy functions such as authentication and authorization techniques and data workflows. Moreover, a description of the standards and protocols implemented in the Ageing@Work system architecture is also provided in the present document.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AR	Augmented Reality
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DREAD	Damage, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected Users, Discoverability
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
REST api	REpresentational State Transfer api
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
VR	Virtual Reality
VUM	Virtual User Models
WAF	Web Application Firewall

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to present privacy and security guidelines in respect to Ageing@Work digital tools' use, the experimental mobile app and the whole architecture of the project. This document also illustrates security and privacy practices and policies that have been considered unanimously by the consortium as crucial in order to ensure data protection from potential malicious threats.

The security and privacy risk analysis performed with regard to each digital tool and overall the Ageing@Work collaborative platform is presented in this document. The main objective has been to establish and implement proper cybersecurity and privacy mechanisms during the overall Ageing@Work system life cycle. To this end, privacy and security-dedicated modules and mechanisms have been developed and implemented in Ageing@Work system to ensure worker data security and privacy. The document provides a digital specific framework to address horizontal issues such as privacy, security, ethical, and legal issues in a consolidated manner across A@W data management and pilot activities. The work presented in the current document places emphasis on trustworthiness of digitized workplaces and secure mechanisms and practices for digital technologies' use.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

The present deliverable is an integral part of security and privacy requirements and aspects as analysed in the deliverable 2.8 Ageing@Work System Architecture. The main objective herein was to achieve the development of robust security and privacy modules with respect to the main components of the Ageing@Work system such as virtual Coach and worker dashboard, AR/VR Tools, knowledge exchange platform, Job Scheduling Tool.

Furthermore, in a more indirect way, this document is related to user requirements as mapped to the Ageing@Work system functionalities and technical specifications (WP2 "User requirements, system specification and architecture and more specifically in D2.2 "enabling and motivating approaches, technologies and current supportive tools" and the D 2.3 "system specifications and architecture").

In addition, this deliverable is related to the D2.4 Ageing@Work Ethics Manual, where information about the ethics by design and by default approach is provided along with the first considerations for assessing processing operations.

The all security and privacy aspects are strong interrelated to the Data Management Plan of Ageing@Work Data Management Plan. To this end, security and privacy aspects of workers' dataset are also analysed in D9.4 Data Management Plan. A detailed description of Ageing@Work datasets was provided in the DMP setting the basis for the holistic security approach that has been defined to be followed from the early beginning of the project.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is as follows: In [Section 2](#) an extensive literature review is presented regarding the security and privacy risks of pervasive technologies in respect to workplaces. Also security and privacy challenges raised by digital technologies' use and with regard to workers' data processing and analysis are described in this section.

[Section 3](#) continues with the description of the A@W framework to elicit trust in users. Subsections of section 4, address security and privacy risks per digital tool. In addition, the security and privacy methodology covering four main points is presented herein:

- Context of data management: a. workplace b. home environment
- Security and Privacy Risks
- Fundamental security and privacy principles
- Validation of data processing

[Section 4](#) analyses A@W security and privacy methodology and the modules in respect to data assets. Furthermore the technical measures as well as the authentication and authorization methods as well as protocols and standards to prevent data linkage are illustrated in its subsections. The deliverable concludes with [section 5](#), which presents an overview of the results obtained so far with regard to security and privacy solutions for the overall Ageing@Work platform use in real-life working environments, while securing and protecting the privacy of older workers.

2. Background and Rationale

2.1 Pervasive technologies: security and privacy risks at workplaces

Over the last decades, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) hold a promising role in empowering humans within workplaces¹. The introduction of digital tools and technological support to organizational environments provides managers and employees with the opportunity to bring such demanding environments under better control². In particular, ICTs can provide new data collection and analysis tools in order to increment the visibility of employee behaviour and collect performance outcomes of employees³. Nonetheless, ICT technologies use overall may be prone to security and privacy risks when used for worker performance appraisal systems⁴.

Recent improvements in computing networking and the internet technologies have led to the development of very powerful internet-connected devices, including sensors, smart phones, cameras and wearables. Wearable IoT devices can be embedded as personal tools for instance to mining workers to provide proper protection from potential hazards⁵. Smart surveillance tools utilizing wearable devices and sensor technologies for tracking workers' data according to the health, location and environmental context of the worker have been used by several companies in the last years⁶.

The use of wearable technologies at work has been introduced as a new form of employees' assessment allowing self-monitor and control abilities for workers' performance improvement and organizations 'productivity aligned with workers' rhythms and needs⁷. Relevant surveys have focused on the individual and organizational impact of the introduction of wearables. In particular, past works have been dedicated mainly on improving workers safety through the surveillance of workers' physical parameters, stimulating physical activity, in terms of programs for wellness and quality of life or detecting work-related stress and fatigue⁸, while others aimed to improve ergonomics⁹. However, the use of wearable technologies brings along privacy considerations provoked mainly by the monitoring capabilities of wearable technologies, as well as the implications of designing monitoring systems of workers¹⁰.

2.2 Personalized digital services and Technical measures for risks' mitigation

2.2.1 Working Environments and ICT technologies

Privacy and security concerns are most likely to be raised in a mass environment such as a workplace due to the fact that the technology for collecting, analyzing and visualizing data can be considered immature¹¹. In particular the collection of vast amount of data raises ethical questions such as how workers' data are used, who has access to the information and monitoring indicators.

2.2.2 Security and Privacy challenges

The use of digital technologies raise a number of considerations and challenges in respect to workers' data analysis and main privacy and security issues such as proper use (proportionality), minimization of data (relevant and suitable data), confidentiality, freedom and autonomy that need to be enabled.

The improvement of the design of workplaces and methods of collecting relevant data to inform such design is among the considerations of developers of diverse work domains. Concrete criteria have been defined to evaluate accessibility, adaptability and iterability of health wearable interfaces. From the perspective of ethics, this involves the cultural tendency of creating 'biotizens'¹², namely gathering information about their body and then sharing that data with others to engage in proactive health self-management. Moreover, wearables use can be connected to socio-ethics challenges for the user. For instance, according to Mittelstadt¹³, the social impact of using such devices for individuals' deals with the stigma that this connection may in turn be associated with a health or disease condition.

2.2.3 Challenges in the COVID- 19 era

Home-based working as part of quarantine measures to reduce the potential exposure to COVID-19¹⁴, can have a tremendous effect on work-life balance¹⁵. In terms of quarantine measures older people have to remain vigilant which is also connected to determinant factors such as the nature of work performed and to personality traits such as discipline and the competence to handle the assigned tasks successfully. Social isolation could be another deterrent factor to workability enhancement of ageing workers, who may feel loneliness and frustration away from their ordinary work culture¹⁶. Moreover, extended digitization of work procedures due to COVID-19 virus, brings new risks such as digital and social inequalities [ref]. Vulnerable populations, including older workers with chronic conditions, due to social isolation or poor socio-economic status, are more exposed to risks¹⁷. Among the most important ethical challenges is to what extent privacy infringement will be justified under the scope of emergency and in which direction monitoring data, will be used and for how long. Considering the marginalization of senior silvers during the COVID-19 pandemic, due to psychological risks such as loneliness, isolation, ageism, and limitations to health care access, remote management of workability factors had to be enabled¹⁸. Ethical considerations in the COVID- 19 era and beyond demand new requirements for ethical frameworks that will be guided by specific contexts of locations, policies, resources and the extent of virus infection. For instance, business models of mild, moderate, severe and critical burden may be proposed. The same ethical principles that have always been used to guide transplant practices continue to apply during the COVID-19 era, but the balance between autonomy, beneficence, no maleficence, and justice depend on the policies, available resources, and local practices put in place. These principles provide a sound basis for a theoretical framework to guide and evaluate the digital well-being of older workers.

3. SmartFrameWork: A privacy by design Security Framework to Elicit Trust in Ageing@Work

The significance of initiating a trustworthy framework of data processing applicable to pervasive technology systems is undeniable. In parallel, taking into account the complexity of workplace environments and the relevance of this complexity with the potential of technology pervasiveness, in the context of workplaces digitization and personalized health support through ICT tools, a significant need emerged for a specific ethics framework. The main notion was to structure a framework for secure data management in the context of Ageing@Work workplaces by incorporating core user-centred principles.

This conceptual framework has to be rigid according to privacy concerns in a number of areas: (a) research engagement and participation; (b) data monitoring and tracking; (c) data processing during and after the study duration; (d) workplace relationships. The convergence point was ‘worker—older adult’ needs and in order to unlock properly these needs, well-known theories have been explored such as the Bloom’s Taxonomy about the Affective Domain to facilitate older workers’ perceptions’ understanding in depth as expressed at feelings, values, appreciation, enthusiasms, motivations, and attitudes. These theoretical specificities shaped the 5-step design of the technologies of the study: (a) receiving with respect older adults perception and doubts; (b) shaping the right and up to the point motivations; (c) demonstrating values and beliefs in a democratic process; (d) organizing values by resolving conflicts; (e) internalizing values by enabling teamwork, enhance commitment to ethical practice and its regular assessment.

The architecture of the proposed framework focuses mainly on the establishment of the foundational principles of “Security by Design” and “Privacy by Design” as presented in Table 1 below. Therefore, secure access to data has been complemented by users’ control over their personal information. From the privacy lens, the main aim was to ensure personal information protection in digitized environments. From the security perspective, to enforce activities that will protect assets of individuals and places.

Table 1. A@W Security and Privacy principles

Foundational Principles	
Privacy by design	Security by Design
<i>Proactive and preventive actions rather than remedial actions</i>	<i>Integrity</i>
<i>Privacy as default setting</i>	<i>Confidentiality</i>
<i>Embedded privacy in A@W architecture</i>	<i>Use of software and hardware solutions such as the data security and privacy module</i>
<i>Transparency</i>	<i>Reliable access to data</i>
<i>Visibility</i>	<i>Reliable use of data</i>
<i>User –centred data management</i>	<i>Indicate respect to users and protect their interests and information</i>
<i>A ‘win –win’¹⁹ approach</i>	<i>Resolve potential conflicts</i>

To this end, a five-step study design has been followed, including privacy and security implications and risks ranging from the engagement process to data governance and the final delivery of research. Among the high considerations were the specific monitoring methods of workers’ behaviour, workability and health status through concrete technologies as well as the context of this monitoring. Furthermore, older workers’ datasets were considered of high value and possibly sensitive activities’ tracking, especially when applied in home environments, has to be defined.

Three pillars supported the theoretical framework: (a) datatype visibility, which entails ethical implications and are mostly prone to conflicts between workplace actors; (b) the actors who enable legitimate access to data and, (c) the scope of monitoring (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The main pillars of the Ageing@Work SmartFrameWork

According to processing operations through ICT usage, the blurred line between working life and activities outside the world has to become clear. Also the use in the workplace of office applications provided as a cloud service, which in theory allows for very detailed logging of the activities of employees along with the use of wearable devices (e.g. health and fitness devices) were protected by a number of measures that have been initiated and implemented on the core principles of ‘limited access to sensitive data’ and unobtrusiveness in AI technology involvement. An ethical canvas has been structured to facilitate the process of potential ethical risks as indicated below (Fig. 3). Initially, standard ethics’ risks have been defined as emerging from the use of mixed emerging technologies along with the risks of ageist stereotypes, bias and discrimination that older adults experience and operate as obstacles in their well-being and health care support. Furthermore, issues of data security and privacy are processed through a Secure and Privacy Framework in compliance with EU legislations (e.g. GDPR) provided the proper structure to manage with the diverse information and data generated within the project duration and in conformity with its main research objectives and targets.

In case, there was no other way to avoid storage of sensitive data within the server. In this case, robust security and organizational measures have been enabled such as limited access to personal and private data. Moreover, these data are defined to be accessible for further analysis and processing only by accredited consortium members.

Since data with ethical implications have been identified along with the ethical canvas of the data management at workplaces, there was also a provision for data fairness by making data accessible, interoperable, and reusable, including provisions for metadata analysis. In particular, the data generated

through the worker activities monitoring platform during the whole lifecycle of the study are provisioned to be discoverable through a centralized database, part of the knowledgebase.

3.1 Security and Privacy Methodology

Privacy and confidentiality in the workplace were among the critical concerns of A@W consortium for both employers and employees. Therefore, in the light of smart working environments an extensive analysis of each digital tool has been conducted in respect to a number of variables including (a) data type, (b) context of data, (c) specific technologies and, (d) actors involved in the collection and processing of this data. This set of categorical variables are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Typology of multimodal datasets

A thorough mapping of A@W data along with the technologies involved guided the identification and understanding of potential risks of data use and the limitations that had to be defined according to social sensitive groups as workers. These specific parameters according to employees’ datasets use that may implicate security and ethical concerns are quoted below:

- Involvement of technologies and techniques that measure human body dimensions;
- Verification of reliability and validity of anthropometric data measurement;
- Sensory problems processing that might be associated with the impact in workability;
- Lifestyle habits’ monitoring as part of public health monitoring;
- Monitoring and measuring occupational health data;
- Measuring occupational health and safety risks.

Security and privacy risk assessment has been considered fundamental in accordance with each phase of the data cycle from the collection, processing, storage, to the analysis and use of data in terms of risk assessment and decision-making. Moreover two clusters of information, (a) overall ethics practices including unclear ‘grey areas’ of AI and VR technologies use and (b) information access, in particular manager rights to this access through the core technologies (i.e. apps’ interfaces, ageing workers virtual user models, etc.) were inclined to high risk for security and data protection.

Given the specific concerns and risks per tools, proper security and privacy modules have been developed based on a concrete security and privacy methodology. The security and privacy methodology regarding data and metadata management of older workers rely upon three dimensions a. worker privacy b. organizational data privacy and c. issues from a macro perspective side (sector-wide/society).

3.1.1 Privacy Methodology in compliance to GDPR

With the advent of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) entered in force on May 25th, 2018 in the European Union, privacy in Europe has gained a lot of visibility. This subsection presents a methodology for performing privacy risks analysis related to privacy modules of the A@W project.

A key step of this methodology was the performance of Data Impact Performance Assessment (DPIA). Both pilots (ANEFA and SIEMENS) have carried out a DPIA in consistency to data protection by design and by default principles.

Common criteria have been followed to carry out a DPIA in compliance with GDPR requirements to set out the following minimum features of a DPIA according to its article 35²⁰.

- A systematic description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing, including, where applicable, the legitimate interest pursued by the controller.
- An assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes.
- An assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects.
- The measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with this Regulation taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned”.
- The process should be documented and executed on the data request and report any issues or data breaches within the guidelines.
- The process should be continuously monitored, reviewed and updated including the procedure for data privacy and protection.

3.1.2 Security and Privacy Modules

In order to prefigure security in A@W services transmission, a thorough mapping of all data along with the technologies involved was valuable in understanding the potential risks of data use and the limitations that had to be defined according to social sensitive groups as older adults and the access to their data.

Initially there was need for in depth understanding of devices and applications involvement in workers’ data collection and how this data are stored and processed in respect to A@W objectives. Therefore, the data flow of smart apps, devices and the overall Digital Platform of A@W project is presented in the figure below.

All the data is collected through the devices and applications of A@W platform. Every component of this system is communicating with the final database with an authenticated RESTful API. Every component has a direct communication with the API, except the smartwatch, which sends the data to the server in a two-step way. The data of the smartwatch are sent to the mobile app and afterwards the mobile app sends the data to the database as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Data Flow diagram of A@W Digital Platform

Data-related risks in respect to A@W assets have been considered in accordance with each phase of the data cycle from the collection, processing, storage, to the analysis and use of data in terms of risks assessment and decision-making. In the current study, specific challenges were faced according to two clusters of information, (a) overall security and privacy practices including unclear ‘grey areas’ of AI and VR technologies use and (b) information access, in particular manager rights to this access through the core technologies (i.e. apps’ interfaces, ageing workers virtual user models, etc.).

Furthermore, the protection of supporting assets such as physical devices implemented in real environments. Digital tools’ functionality, which rely on smartphone apps, wi-fi networks, internet and additional supporting assets such as users’ premises have been taken of considered of high importance.

3.1.3 Data assets' identification and analysis

A thorough identification of number of categorical variables, including (a) data type, (b) context of data, (c) specific technologies and, (d) actors involved in the collection and processing of these data and multimodal datasets processed in the context of smart work environments has been carried out, a typology has been specified according to a number of categorical variables, including (a) data type, (b) context of data, (c) specific technologies and, (d) actors involved in the collection and processing of this data (Figure 4).

Figure 4. A@W data assets' identification

The outcome of this analysis were specific parameters according to workers' datasets use that may implicate security and ethical concerns. In particular the involvement of technologies and techniques that measure human body dimensions, verification of reliability and validity of anthropometric, data measurement, sensory problems processing that might be associated with the impact in workability, lifestyle habits' monitoring as part of public health monitoring, monitoring and measuring occupational health data measuring occupational health and safety risks.

3.1.4 Security at a physical layer: Authentication and authorization functions

Authentication is the process of determining whether someone or something is, in fact, who or what it claims or is declared to be. Authorization is in fact the process of giving someone permission to do or to have something. This implies that in order to be able to give someone access to something this someone needs first to be authenticated. Authorization is in fact the process of giving someone permission to do or to have something. This implies that in order to be able to give someone access to something this someone needs first to be authenticated²¹.

Authentication and authorization practices are typically related to access’ management and permission operations. Access management has to ensure security of resources on servers and during communication secure data authenticity. IP authentication and password-based access are the main authentication methods, however not being the panacea to protect content duplication or sharing.

In respect to digital technologies, a number of indicators have to be analyzed such as the type and objective of repository, type of digital content, security of the system, security of communication channel, diversity of users’ platform, number of users, and the perceptions and responses of end users²².

Furthermore concerning the mobile environment, the issue of authentication and authorization is more complex.

After a thorough study of effective authentication and authorization mechanisms in respect to digital environments, a list of security properties/criteria have been defined, [Table 2](#), in order to possess a good authentication and authorization mechanism.

Table 2: Security criteria for user authentication and authorization

Correctness	<i>The result of user authentication and authorization should be correct</i>
Possibility of anonymity and privacy	<i>In cases authorization is possible without users’ identity disclosure, it should be done that way</i>
Speed	<i>The authentication process should be fast</i>
Attack resistance	<i>The authentication mechanism should be attack resistant</i>
User friendliness	<i>The authentication mechanism should have as little overhead as possible to the user.</i>

At the early beginning of A@W project, a main concern of responsibilities was the guidance and monitoring of actions in respect to secure and privacy protected authentication schemes.

To this end, a twofold approach based on technical robustness and administrative policy guided how the digital repositories’ content will be accessed and shared in conformity to legitimate use.

In this context, secure data transmission in A@W context is related to authentication of functional components (strong passwords, by default credentials), authenticated connections, authenticated code source and data authentication. Authentication is mandatory before any privileged operation. The authentication technique that we used is oauth2 which is the industry standard protocol for authorization. We used passport library and especially Laravel Passport Library which is a full OAuth2 server implementation for Laravel Framework. In order to authenticate we created a login service in which user sends his email and password. The service then use the Auth::attempt() function which converts the email & password to hashes with bcrypt function and compares them with the saved one in the database. If the hashes match, then the authentication is successful, and we create an oauth2 token by using the passport library. With this token the user is capable to make calls in the api authenticated.

For the authorization we built a role based authorization approach. Every new user in the system has its own role. Every request of the RESTful api is authorized and then responded with a suitable response. For example if a request should be only visible to the admin of the system and a worker is trying to fetch data he will get a 401 Response which means he is not authorized. We created a series of authorization

functions in the system and one of the most useful was `userHasRole()`, which checks the current authenticated user's role.

3.1.5 Integrity confidentiality and Availability

In terms of a trustful digital environment, architecture design should guarantee that based on the principle of 'security by design' will reflect five principles: a. confidentiality, authentication authorization integrity and availability.

Confidentiality entails that only the legitimate recipient of data should have visibility of data. Authentication ensures that in each connection to a system user identity is known. Integrity provides proof that a message's content has not been modified either by intention or intention since it was sent.

In alignment with security and privacy specification, the security and privacy module of the A@W system reflected the following requirements:

- **Authorization:** specific rules defined to assign the proper persons/entities who are authorized to have access and/or modify workers' information.
- **Authentication:** secure who will be the communication peer.
- **Integrity:** Concern data and service authenticity, secure that data will not be modified during transmitting accidentally or intentionally
- **Confidentiality:** ensure that worker data cannot be available to any third party

Key security properties that include integrity in A@W system is verified and validated mechanisms related to user transactions. For instance, strong passwords used in the entire system have been created and put in place in order to avert untrusted files. Also, the web server update and maintenance is always trying to use the stable version with all patches. Moreover, additional integrity requirements have been defined such as a. an update policy (firmware update) b. software update mechanisms c. monitoring and alerting capability to system potential malfunction.

3.1.6 Risk assessment Models

In order to identify and evaluate potential attacks on each digital component, a security risk assessment method has been followed on the basis of well-known and validated models such as the DREAD Model (Damage, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected Users, and Discoverability). In the content of A@W for each threat, a mitigation solution was initiated, and finally a compliance class was computed.

3.1.7 Robust techniques for data protection and privacy preserving personal information

In order to implement robust authentication and authorization schemes, different techniques of data protection and privacy preserving of personal data access and storage have been studied and analyzed along with the EU perspective on the techniques of de-identification and encryption.

From the early beginning of the project, there was a provision of anonymization techniques in line with strict privacy and security preserving policies (D2.8 A@W System Architecture). However, given that the main goal of A@W was to acquire personalized information, fully anonymized data was not considered as

proper to be applied as a single method. To address this issue, especially in the context of Ageing@Work, privacy and security framework refinement in respect to data aggregation tools, techniques of security and privacy have been applied in alignment with the contextual factors and the purposes of the A@W project. Therefore, a well-known data management technique highly recommended by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the technique of de-identification has been applied in the industrial and working environment through unique identifiers tied to authorized users.

The technique of encryption has been implemented to provide the personalized information while overall the technique of anonymization will be applied in the context of dataset's analysis after pilots' operation.

Overall, Ageing@Work is consistent with a minimal approach to data collection for personalization. This means that by default all personal data will remain de-identified, nonetheless access and use of individual-level data would be possible in certain cases in order to be reversible solely for responsible and authorized researchers and entities.

The main strategy in order to compromise personalization services with privacy risks was to initiate user-side personalization. Concerning the category of sensitive data such as exact location coordinates used by decision algorithms, an unanimous decision of the consortium was to not allow this information sharing with an external server. On the other hand, relevant functions to export the above data are necessary, for various reasons, including:

- to allow workers to exercise their rights under art. 20 of the GDPR and obtain a copy of the data that the system controls about them in machine-readable format.
- to possibly reuse the data – with user consent and according to FAIR principles – to support further analyses, in addition to those allowed by the Visual Analytics component of Ageing@Work, with the aim of conducting studies beyond the scope of Ageing@Work (e.g., in OSH research)

Within Ageing@Work a de-identification approach was used in order to keep sensitive data and individuals' identity private and secure²³. Data privacy and authentication schemes could be better understood in relation to the specific tasks of WP4. More specifically in the context of T4.1 'Open and extensive framework for worker activity and behavior tracking and T4.2 task, 'Unobtrusive worker activity and behavior monitoring', an unobtrusive worker activity and behavior monitoring framework has been designed to understand the old worker's interests, behavioral factors in work and home environments in a secure and privacy protected way.

Thereafter, in the context of A@W digital infrastructure, concrete strategies and techniques had to be implemented in order to frame trust in information sources from workers, in respect to documents and technologies use (e.g. virtual agents).

Given the diversity of components and information systems, along with the sensitivity of data, a flexible mix mechanism, a hybrid solution, has been followed in respect to data access in order to ensure data privacy whilst benefiting for system personalization features.

On the one hand, de-identification has been considered as a critical privacy measure while processing and sharing sensitive data to prevent re-identification and enforce disclosure control. Furthermore, encryption schemes²⁴ have been also implemented in order to provide confidentiality²⁵.

To this end, in this data and their annotations about specific workers' activity, the method of de-identification has been applied. Workplace models do not include personal information. However there is

provision if such case arises, data de-identification is enforced before their use. Moreover, data, which have been defined to be available on the web after the conclusion of the pilot studies, are also de-identified. Full anonymization of data will also be considered after the completion of the trials, in case that data is shared with third parties for research purposes.

However also the technique of encryption has been implemented in cases that personal information has been considered critical in terms of the project research purposes. In this case, only authorized access has been permitted. Encryption has been considered a safe method for data to be hidden from the third party or any potential attack²⁶. More specifically, in order to enable the security of RESTful services, strong encryption schemes and a REST security protocol have been implemented. In this respect, the whole encryption of the RESTful api we have is provided by Laravel Framework. Laravel's encryption services provide a simple, convenient interface for encrypting and decrypting text via OpenSSL using AES-256 and AES-128 encryption. All of Laravel's encrypted values are signed using a message authentication code (MAC) so that their underlying value cannot be modified or tampered with once encrypted. In the A@W server we created an application key in order to achieve this encryption. For example if you want to encrypt a token you call `Crypt::encryptString()` function and when you want to decrypt something you call `Crypt::decryptString()`.

Furthermore, an additional layer of security was added to the existing system by adding a Web Application Firewall (WAF). Specifically, since the VUM web application was written in the Laravel framework, shieldon(<https://shieldon.io/en>) WAF used to control and manage the firewall rules and security settings of the system. Moreover, the system administrator of the VUM web application will be able to check the network logs and maintain the security of the system by using the friendly User Interface provided by shieldon.

3.1.8 Risks' impact assessment and robust security controls

An effective risk assessment and management process was considered critical component in order to provide a secure digital platform in the context of A@W project. The principal goal was to identify the potential threats, define proper technical measures accordingly and initiate security features and controls for datasets' protection.

A Risk impact assessment has been conducted as depicted in the table below concerned both device software and hardware (Table 3).

Table 3. Risk impact assessment towards a secure digital platform

Potential Threats	Mitigation technology	Technical mitigation measures	Features

Spoofing	Authentication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong authentication at registration • Authentication for every data transfer between mobile application and server 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login with strong passwords, no default credentials • Authenticated connections for every data transfer
Tampering	Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules in database: data validation • Access Control to modify sensitive information by certain roles (explain further) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity management through concrete roles' assignment (e.g. administrator, health personnel, manager)
Information disclosure	Confidentiality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSL • Encrypted storage of data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defensive mechanisms in databases • Access restrictions to sensitive information • Access control (need to know method)
	Availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection from against malicious access to the system
	Authorization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access in data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available only in certain roles
Security controls in user interface			
	Authentication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login with a certain password 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authenticity entities

3.2 Security policies, standards and protocols

Secure policies and methods such as security by default and security controls in respect to software installation and configuration have been enabled within A@W project. Security by default has been ensured by limited access to information, systems and devices/apps solely to data needed for A@W research purposes. From a broader perspective, the security policies that have been followed are depicted in Figure 5:

Figure 5. A@W main security policies

Standards and protocols that are used, integrate various levels of security protection guided the adoption of security measures and effective practices for privacy preservation. In the context of A@W project security and privacy activities contributed in respect to a. technological deployment of digital tools for workability and productivity enhancement b. societal that is to introduce smart environments for ageing workers.

3.3 Strong interconnection between security and privacy

The interrelation between privacy and security in terms of digitized environments has long been recognized. However they are also addressed also in silos²⁷. The development of the advanced, personalized and adaptive ICT tools of the Ageing@Work, that aim at improving the wellbeing and productivity on the basis of AI, AR/VR, and IoT wearable devices security and privacy interconnection, have been based on fundamental key areas identified on the A@W framework:

- Security Principles
- User access and authorization credentials
- Transparency in Data Management

In order to have a clear overview of the security and privacy threats in respect to the clusters of information mentioned above, data processed in the context of each tool has to be screened extensively. This information is analysed in the following section.

4. Security and privacy issues per tool from technical lens

In the context of A@W digital framework, the proposed system had to be protected by sophisticated cyberattacks. Initially it was of high importance to understand the technical difference between web application firewalls and network level firewalls, which is related to the layer of security they operate on. Web Application Firewall (WAF) solutions protect businesses from web-based attacks targeted at applications. WAF solutions protect businesses from web-based attacks targeted at applications. Network firewalls protect against unauthorized access and traffic coming into and out of the network²⁸.

These combined solutions may decrease servers' capacity and performance; however, a detailed analysis has been carried out in order to use effective firewalls against web and internet potential attacks. In the following subsections Hypertext Transfer Protocols (HTTP) used in respect to each component of the A@W system to detect and block malicious threats.

4.1 VUM server

The VUM backend service is a RESTful API with a MySQL database which represents the central repository of data for Ageing@Work. The VUM backend is a web application written in the Laravel framework¹, which enables extensibility and offers great community support. The web application is deployed under an Ubuntu Linux server which contains an Apache2 server and a MySQL server. The Apache2 server is using encryption through the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol for all Internet communications, and all the HTTP requests are secured (HTTPS). Also, in the Ubuntu linux server we added a firewall in which we blocked 3306 which is the port of MySQL in order to be accessible only inside the local network. In fact the only aloud port outside of the server is 80 which is responsible to server Apache2. The TLS certificates were generated using the nonprofit Certificate Authority LetsEncrypt², and they are automatically updated before their expiration. The backend service has both authentication and authorization.

4.2 Virtual Coach Mobile Application

We use JSON web tokens (JWT) as token format³, which is an open, industry standard RFC 7519 method for representing claims securely between two parties, for authentication purposes. We also use the Laravel passport library, which provides a full OAuth2 implementation, as an industry protocol for the secure transfer of tokens. In order to be authenticated every component calls the login request in which provides

¹ <https://laravel.com/>

² <https://letsencrypt.org/>

³ <https://jwt.io/>

the email and password of the desired user, and when it's submitted the response of the request contains an access token an expiration date and a refresh token. For the authorization we create a role system in the backend and in every request we check the permissions of each user. Also, all the API requests validate their inputs. Virtual Coach Mobile Application

The Ageing@Work Virtual Coach mobile application (Figure 6) was developed in Android and represents the main worker tool for data collection and population of the VUM, along with provision of Virtual Coach recommendations. The Android ecosystem ensures users are aware of the sensory data access and requires user's explicit consent for the usage/access of each sensor. Moreover, in order to access data provided by third parties, such as Google Fit and Samsung Health, users must provide additional consents. Furthermore, within the application, the workers need to provide their consent, after being informed about the categories of data being collected, so as to allow the transfer of data from the mobile phone towards the server. This measure ensures that the users have been informed about the data collection policy and agree that their applicable data will also be stored at the VUM server.

Figure 6. Virtual Coach services in the A@W Mobile app interface

The data being collected on the mobile phone are stored on the application's internal storage which is only available for the Ageing@Work application itself. This is essentially a protected Android Application Sandbox, which isolates the application's data and code execution from other apps. This is a native Android implementation used by most of applications and it's considered as is considered a sufficient protection measure. In contrast to the Internal Storage, the External Storage does not provide security and its usage was avoided as to protect worker's data against unwanted data access.

The data collected during the usage of the application are populating the Virtual User Model (VUM) database, and the users can overview them through the Clinical Platform API. All the components and their properties are depicted in Figure 7.

Name	Data	Details
Location Tracking Library	Latitude, Longitude, Address	Uses cellular network or GPS. Methods for geocoding and battery optimizations
Activity Tracking Library	Google Activity Recognition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Walking, Still, Running, In Vehicle, On Bicycle, Tilting CNN model: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Walking, Still, Upstairs, Downstairs Step Counter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steps, Activity Intensity, Calories, METs 	Googles Activity Recognition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orientation/Position independent. Battery optimization implemented. CNN based on UCI HAR dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orientation/Position depended. Battery restricted. Step Counter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides step counting updates every few seconds.
Location Context API	Locations Category and Subcategory	Custom API that uses OpenStreetMap's files to categorize locations.
Keyboard	Press/Release Time, Distance, Deletion	Uses AOSP keyboard files modified to record keystroke Time Sequences.
Self-Reports	Demographics, Questionnaires	Users are prompted to answer self-administered questionnaires periodically and demographic related questions.
Clinical Platform API	Weight, Humidity, Luminescence, Temperature, Blood pressure, Blood Glucose, Questionnaires	Receives IoT derived data and store them under strict protocols. Offers data visualization over aggregated periods and management tools for the administration (e.g. add new Questionnaires).
Samsung Accessory SDK	Raw data : Accelerometer, Gyroscope, Heart rate	Provides methods for raw data retrieval from Samsung Smartwatches.
Samsung Health SDK	Steps, Water intake, Activities, Floors Climbed, Heart rate, Sleep stages	Provides various health / activity related data while using Samsung phone or smartwatch.
Google Fit	Steps, Sleep Metrics, Activities, Heart rate	Provides various health / activity related data while using an Android phone.
Virtual User Model (VUM)	Provides: Login credentials Stores: All the non-sensitive data above	All the above data, collected by the middleware, are stored on an SQLite database inside the phone. Periodically, if Wi-Fi is available, these data are sent to VUM. Additionally, methods for a notification broadcast system are provided.

Figure 7. VUMs datasets' screening

The architecture of the mobile app is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 8. Mobile app data flow

One of the most important parts of the application's functionality is considered to be the location tracking. In order to obtain useful information about worker's location without providing the exact address or latitude and longitude to the server, two measures were implemented. First, as an alternative to the exact

location it was decided to use the location's categorization instead. To this end, an external API was created that receives a latitude-longitude pair and returns, if applicable, a category and subcategory for this location. This API, named "Location Categorization API", was hosted within a separate and protected docker environment which does not require user authentication. As such, the location context can be retrieved without identifying the worker sending it. Additionally, in order to store the address information in an anonymous way, as to be able to recognize unique places visited by the worker even after the reset/reinstall of the application which would erase the numerical order of the stored locations, an SHA-256 encryption of the address string combined with users' password was used. This method results to a non-reversible encryption of the actual address, which is also personalized for each specific worker. That means that if two separate workers sent the same encrypted address, there would be no way of knowing they are at the same location since during the encryption their passwords were also used, thus alternating the final result even if the original address was the same. This method was also used for the encryption of outgoing/incoming phone call numbers, as to be able to extract socialization features (e.g. number of unique phone numbers called), without the need of the actual numbers. Using these methods limited server's access to raw personal sensitive data such as exact locations and phone numbers, but is still able to use alternatives of them to extract valuable features.

Concerning the communication with the server an authentication mechanism is being used on every single request. After the successful login of the worker within the application an access token is returned by the server. This token must be included to each and every one of the requests as to be able to access or transfer data from and to the server. Each token has an expiration date and as such the application needs to either refresh it by using provided mechanisms, or the user would have to re-login. Finally, the communication protocol used is HTTPS to add an additional security layer of SSL encryption over HTTP.

4.3 Worker Dashboard

Worker dashboard is hosting a representation of the collected data aggregated per day or week and additional useful information related to worker's goals and questionnaire answers. Security and reliability of data were considered as dependent on the authentication mechanisms. The main security policies initiated and implemented were clear authentication, and access methods and protection of the physical and software security of the data. In order for this WebView to have access with the data, the application's access token is being used, thus ensuring that the worker will be able to view his own data and only after successful login through the app. The dashboard is integrated within the main application using a browser to open the site. The communication link is using HTTPS protocol and receives the access token from the application as to not require for the worker to login every time. Then this access token is used for each and every single request made from the Dashboard to the VUM server, to receive the data.

4.4 Manager Platform

The manager platform is an angular web application which is served with apache2 in a Ubuntu Linux server 18.04.5 LTS. The Apache2 is configured to use encryption via https (tls) and redirect all http requests to https. Therefore, encryption of information during communication of info is being utilized to protect the

data and the privacy of the users. All the communication with the backend is achieved using JSON web token (JWT) Authentication & Authorization for the different roles of users. JWT is an open standard (RFC 7519) that defines a compact and self-contained way of securely transmitting information between parties. Therefore, secure authorization of users is ensured.

The main security and privacy aspects in respect to this digital tool was how to define in a clear way against potential conflicts the border lines between manager rights to worker data access through the core technologies (i.e. apps' interfaces, ageing workers virtual user models, etc.) and workers' rights.

The main technical mitigation measures were to implement a Secure Apache2 Server with HTTPS protocol (SSL encryption) provided by LetsEncrypt & redirect every HTTP request into HTTPS. Communication with the API with JWT Authentication. Authentication and authorization for those who have access to medical data by providing firewalls, data encryption, and password protection. Enable contingency plans.

4.5 AR Tools

The AR Telepresence Tool is using the main backend of Ageing@Work with JWT Authentication. All the Requests are authenticated and authorized to the needed roles. The tool is also integrated with the manager platform with the same way. The communication of the back-end is over HTTP and tls. Also for the part of the sockets we used wss protocol & authentication using the back-end JWT Authentication. In respect to the AR Situational Awareness Tool the main security concerns emerge by the smartphone camera use therefore user interaction had to be protected sufficiently.

4.6 Knowledge sharing and VR Lifelong Learning

Regarding the security and protection from fraud and abuse whilst navigating and interacting with the KEP Platform, Google's reCAPTCHA service has been employed for both register and login functionality. In the figure below (Figure 9) we can see that the user needs to click the rectangle button to validate that he is a human user and not a robot. To differentiate between humans and bots, this service employs advanced risk analysis techniques.

Figure 9 Google's reCAPTCHA on register and login screen

The security issue in the VR application is addressed by running the application in a local – isolated environment while, at the same time, heavily restricting the information exchange between the VR simulation and the KEP Platform. To elaborate, the total amount of requests from the VR simulation (both POST and GET) are targeted towards specific URLs of the KEP platform to avoid any bot activity by redirecting them to other sites.

Regarding the privacy of the user’s credentials, as it can be shown above, in both KEP platform and the VR experience, the passwords are hidden by default and can be shown only if the user wants it. Apart from the nicknames, no other credentials are exposed to the public, as shown below (Figure 10):

Figure 10. The KEP Platform Interface

Moreover, in the simulation, when the user quits the application, no credentials are being saved, thus no one can have unauthorized access. The same feature has been applied to the KEP platform, where credentials are not saved if the user does not select this option.

4.7 Knowledge Exchange Platform

Authentication from server side & Google Captcha Human Verification. The KEP server side is a dockerized component exposed in a local port and then proxied with a Secure Apache2 Server with HTTPS protocol provided by LetsEncrypt. Every HTTP request is redirected to HTTPS. For authentication purposes, we have applied Simple Server Side Authentication with Google Captcha Human Verification.

4.8 Job Scheduling Tool

Job Scheduling is an algorithm which is served as a restful API in a private network environment. This API is then called from our backend in the private network with all the ports aborted from our firewall. We used firewall to restrict the API in a private network.

5. Conclusion

The results of A@W security and privacy components are provided in this deliverable. The set of A@W security requirements and measurements are presented in here in a consolidated way. Moreover, data assets and supporting assets have been analysed in order to understand thoroughly risks related to A@W datasets' use and corresponding limitations. A detailed mapping of risks has been conducted using digital tools to identify components that hide vulnerabilities and indicate security and privacy strategies and countermeasures to reduce potential risks. Furthermore, security and privacy practices are highlighted to provide information about the A@W preventive strategies, measures and procedures in order to manage effectively potential data breach and linkage.

This work has been conducted to determine which technical solutions are the most proper to be implemented in compliance with the security methodology and frame as has been predefined at a conceptual level. To this end common authentication and authorization schemes have been developed, implemented for the Ageing@Work platform and validated within the Ageing@Work project in respect to digital infrastructures in order to assess the level of security required according to diverse assets (e.g. devices, apps).

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